

The Bauhaus of the Seas

a Manifesto for the New European Bauhaus

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This paper describes the Bauhaus of the Seas (BoS) Manifesto, a vision for the New European Bauhaus (NEB), which aims to address the challenges of the European Green Deal by fostering sustainability, regeneration, social inclusion, and beauty. We describe this initiative to promote ethical, economic, cultural, spatial, and aesthetic regenerative development in our relationship with water bodies. By emphasizing non-anthropocentric design principles, the BoS incorporates diverse voices and fosters a more holistic perspective on design. The Manifesto proposes an exploration of an entangled co-design process, caring drops, and hydrocommon ripples demonstrate a commitment to address contemporary design challenges while connecting with ecofeminism, humanistic HCI, and decolonizing design.

Additional Keywords and Phrases: New European Bauhaus, Sustainability, More than Humans, Ocean

1 PREAMBLE

In the fall of 2020, the authors of the Manifesto gathered as a working group to propose a vision for the New European Bauhaus (NEB) from Portugal. The authors met for the first time to discuss how the NEB, based on sustainability, social inclusion, and beauty, could be interpreted from a peripheral European country with a longstanding natural, cultural, and historical connection to the Ocean. Coming from many different disciplines, designers, architects, engineers, and lovers of surf and nature share a common vision manifested here. The Bauhaus of the Seas manifesto the follow-up research projects, and pilot initiatives are the outcomes of these efforts, which are currently evolving in seven different coastal cities across Europe spanning different aquatic ecosystems (the Tagus River estuary in Portugal, the Lagoon of Venice and the Gulf of Genova in Italy, the Rhine-Schedt delta in the Netherlands and Belgium and the Øresund strait in Sweden). Across these pilots, the BoS will explore radical innovation approaches called drops. Multispecies assemblies fostering cooperation between humans and non-humans, regenerative menus bridging gastronomy, architecture, and design to introduce ecologically sensitive diets, blue makerspaces serving as innovative laboratories sustainably integrating marine-based residues into urban designs and wellbeing reefs providing tools and insights to design sub-aquatic habitats that cater to

both humans and marine life, and lastly inclusive digital storytelling employing AI and AR technologies to share geolocated stories that bridge cultural divides, emphasising the importance of multicultural and interspecies understanding.

2 THE NEW EUROPEAN BAUHAUS

The New European Bauhaus (NEB) aims to address the challenges of the European Green Deal by fostering sustainability, regeneration, social inclusion, and beauty. Here we present a manifesto for a Bauhaus of the Seas (BoS), an initiative to promote ethical, economic, cultural, spatial, and aesthetic regenerative development in our relationship with water bodies. The Bauhaus defined the role of design in the 20th century by combining art and architecture with industry and construction embedded in a political/economic/social vision of the world after the First World War. Launched by the European Commission in 2020, the New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative aims to promote implementing the European Green Deal (policy to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050) based on sustainability, social inclusion, and beauty. This means realizing regenerative approaches inspired by nature that enrich our experiences through creativity, art, and culture, embracing diversity to promote inclusive, accessible spaces where the dialogue between diverse cultures, disciplines, genders, ethnicities, and life stages becomes an opportunity to imagine a better future for all.

2.1 THE BAHAUS OF THE SEAS

The climate crisis is a global, complex hyperobject arising from the deeply entrenched belief in human exceptionalism and the artificial dichotomy between humans and nature. In response to this urgent challenge, the Bauhaus of the seas, interpreted from the Portuguese word “Mar” (sea) as “marhaus” (“the sea as our home”) or “baumar” (“the sea as a space for creation”), endeavors to foster a holistic and transformative approach to our connection with the ocean.

Departing from the concept of hydrocommons, BoS fosters a fluid understanding of the intricate connections between humans and nonhumans, advocating for non-anthropocentric design principles stemming from ecofeminism. The journey of the Bauhaus of the Seas (BoS), proposed as a [manifesto to the first NEB co-design conference](#), is organised in five anchors:

- **Recognizing the environment** by mapping the interdependencies of flows of mineral, biological and human (food, transport, communities, and migrations) resources, parameterizing, optimising, and digitising data for informed and sustainable management and informed decision making and communicating about their relevance;
- **Reconciling with the sea** by connecting with the waters as a territory of trans-geographic continuity through site-specific ecosystems that host unique entanglements of humans and non-humans, opening new possibilities to the strategic needs of the NEB;
- **Reconnecting communities** with their habitats and forms of material, ecological, aesthetic and cultural heritage, supporting the generation and co-creation of fresh ideas, emerging from the interdependence between species, generations and culture and oriented towards mutual admiration and respect capable of nourishing a truly sustainable blue economy;
- **Renewing practises** by engaging citizens in the sustainable management of local resources through the resurgence of fresh modes of co-ownership, caring and stewardship that contribute to a heightened sense of belonging and sharing responsibility and innovative artistic, experiential, material and technological interventions, replicable globally and welcoming decolonialism acknowledging diversity, difference, and the multiplicity of identities and subjectivities;
- **Storytelling actions** that narrate and connect the findings developed across the journey to effectively enact a prefigurative counterpower of systems and spaces the NEB aims to achieve, exposing multiple perspectives,

discussing ethical challenges and pointing towards alternative and sustainable futures to our seas, ocean and water bodies.

The BoS seeks to acknowledge the diverse knowledge in coastal and marine communities and ecosystems. It aims to unleash its innovative potential for renewal and adaptation through design and creativity, aligning with a new generation of practices and policies focused on cooperation and transnational problem-solving. By navigating contemporary culture, discourses, and technologies, the BoS strives to forge tangible pathways for action based on a critical understanding of the complexities of the seas as a realm of research and practice.

Thus, the BoS introduces an ecocentric narrative that blends cosmopolitanism with a deep connection to nature-based solutions. It embraces a plural and testimonial approach, employing design principles to address complex socio-technical-ecological challenges that are significant for the UN's Sustainable Development Goals. The BoS aims to foster the design of intricate interactions between humans and non-human entities, transcending traditional notions of fixing and growth towards nurturing and contingency. By embracing this agenda, designers, architects, and engineers can reimagine assemblages rather than rigid systems, shifting the focus from extinction to the precarious flourishing of life. The design of these interactions generates new aesthetics and cultivates critical awareness of the past, present, and future, extending our design perspectives beyond the human realm to ensure the sustainability of our shared future.

Figure 1: The Bauhaus of the Seas

2.2 A New Bauhaus for the Green Deal

The New European Bauhaus is a promising concept for the European Green Deal, aiming to retool Europe's design capabilities to address environmental challenges. The project requires a coherent design process focusing on principles and perspectives rather than specific solutions. As a top-down vision, the NEB was not without criticism shortly after being presented by the European Commission President in late 2020. Despite the concerns about the historical reading of the socio-political context of the original Bauhaus focused on rebuilding Europe as a continent of nations after the first world war, Eurocentric modernism, and worries about the EU influencing the funding of arts and culture, the NEB is seen as a

tool that can tap into the imaginative potential of the arts and foster a culture that shapes public life in a more equitable and resilient manner.

The Bauhaus of the Seas (BoS) manifesto attempts to refocus the NEB's goals on contemporary design issues, particularly human and more-than-human interactions, values, and our relationship with water bodies. The BoS emphasizes a post-anthropocentric approach in policymaking for sustainable cities, promoting co-ownership, stewardship, and innovative interventions. This initiative tackles broader themes of recognizing the environment, reconciling with water bodies, reconnecting communities, and narrative actions.

The BoS adopts the concept of "Zoöps"¹, a model that promotes cooperation between human and non-human life, and changes organizational decision-making by appointing an advisor called a "Speaker of the Living". Moreover, it draws from Kamau Brathwaite's "tidalectics"², considering the cyclical movement of water as a model of thought to challenge nature/culture divides and create a regenerative, non-extractive economy. Ultimately, it serves as an empowering and culturally sensitive endeavor addressing the intricate challenges of our relationship with water bodies and ecological sustainability.

3 THE BAUHAUS OF THE SEAS APPROACH

The Bauhaus of the Seas approach includes an entangled co-design process, emphasizing the interconnectedness of design, technology, built environment, culture, identity, and governance, aiming to include diverse voices and interests while preventing polarization. The core of the approach is the concept of "caring drops," which creates more responsible, accountable, and ethical patterns of engaging the environment by incorporating other-than-human life into design processes. Drops enable designers to operate simultaneously at multiple scales and consider human and non-human stakeholders, fostering a more holistic and ethical perspective of the environments they are working with. BoS proposes replicating small-scale cases of transformative creative practices via "hydrocommon ripples", which involve using "water bodies ambassadors" to foster diversity, social learning, and grounding the project in the communities it aims to involve to ensure long-term legacy. Ripples foster community transformation within small groups, using a self-replicating system grounded in mutual care rather than traditional transactional relationships. The BoS initiative envisions a shared, more thoughtful, and caring approach to design and development concerning water bodies and their critical ecosystems, aligning with the NEB's vision for the European Green Deal.

¹ This cooperative model that makes the interests of nonhuman life part of organizational decision-making was originally developed at the New Institute (HNI) in the Netherlands by Klaas Kuitenbrouwer, who are currently partners of BoS to expand the scope and practice of this initiative.

² [1]

...intergenerational, interspecies and intercultural

Figure 2: Visualization of the Bauhaus of the Seas Approach

An approach emphasizing new relations, such as the "more-than-human," should prioritize meaningful inclusion and consider the local context where engagements occur. It is, therefore, essential to pay close attention to how decisions are formed in these processes, which perspectives and interests are prioritized, and what may be overlooked or neglected along the way. This helps avoid the risk of incorporating diverse viewpoints to legitimize the usual players' solutions and decisions, often determined in advance. Specifically, by adopting "caring drops" to represent culturally inspired and locally grounded solutions to recurring problems, it aims to carefully and constantly monitor interactions between humans and nature. Aligned with BoS core values, caring drops encompass prototypes and blueprints that significantly influence our relationship towards healthy water ecosystems through, for example, regenerative food systems and reefs. As a Zoöp host, each caring drop appoints a "Speaker for the Living" to incorporate the interests of other-than-human life into its actions.

Figure 3: The BoSS Pilots with Drops and Ripples

4 THE MANIFESTO

Building a “culture of the Bauhaus of the seas” will involve fostering a school of interdisciplinary experimentation and entrepreneurship, bound to shape a generation of designers, architects, engineers, artists, managers, and scientists around sustainable design solutions for coastal regions and the sea. Support for networked projects should promote the articulation of entities from academic, scientific and cultural systems, incubators, and technological centers, and guide the involvement of the communities in which they operate, with the ultimate goal of creating and recalibrating the capacity to replicate sustainable or regenerative solutions.

Operationalization should address the sea as a source and destination for design, brought to life through the following guidelines:

- Designing and disseminating sustainability models, applicable to local and global scales, that establish continuity between marine and terrestrial ecosystems, including human and more-than-human agents (e.g., animals and protected areas, but also beaches, dunes, and waves);
- Acknowledging and disseminating cross-border paradigms of thought and action, emancipated from a strictly geopolitical mapping, thus contributing to intercultural and radically cosmopolitan visions between contemporary and ancestral, European and trans-European communities and cultures. In this respect, the sea appears as the primary tangible embodiment of a trans-national agenda;
- Promoting innovative forms of reconstruction and representation in architecture and planning, from coastal protection structures to environmentally responsible infrastructures for sustainable management of renewable energies and offshore platforms for aquaculture, including new bio- and geo-materials;
- Promoting and enabling experimentation and food innovation through ecological production and consumption, alternative and/or local practices, implemented through cultural dissemination activities;

- Collecting, structuring, and disseminating testimonies, narratives, knowledge, and objects intimately rooted in past and present experience with the sea – involving historians, anthropologists, sociologists, designers, artists, digital and audiovisual media specialists, collections, and museums in this process of building critical mass;
- Establishing transdisciplinary teams to anticipate and resolve the impact of rising seas and oceans in cities and coastal territories, as well as responses to increasing extreme weather phenomena;
- Developing transdisciplinary missions towards the reversal of the historical trend of using carbon-intensive terrestrial materials (e.g., cement), combining the promotion of natural materials (e.g., wood or hemp used in rigging and candles) and aquatic tools in terrestrial environments (e.g., algae, jellyfish, marine collagen);
- Replacing natural sedimentary cycles, implementing new transfer systems and innovative interventions that promote the development of habitats and the regeneration of marine ecosystems, in order to prevent flooding, erosion, and intrusion of saltwater;
- Encouraging trans-European exchanges and circulation of coastal-inland knowledge through artistic and ethnographic residencies, using museum networks while promoting their respective deactivated and/or outdoor spaces;

5 A SCHOOL SHIP

Imagine a floating school, a pioneering natural sanctuary traversing the vast expanse of the ocean. This innovative institution embarks on a seafaring adventure, accompanied by a vibrant community of emerging creatives and adorned with a collection of "courtesy flags," symbolizing unity under the UN flag representing countries worldwide. Its voyage takes it from the coastal cities of the European Union to the far-flung island territories, bridging the gap between the Classical Age and the unexplored frontiers of the New World. With its registration tracing back to the very shores where the navigation technologies of square sails from the northern seas and triangular sails from the south intersected, this ship represents a testament to the birth of a global community.

Beyond its pedagogical purpose, this extraordinary school embraces an exploration of perspective inversion. It encourages a fresh outlook on the land as seen from the vastness of the sea. As the ship sails onward, it offers a new vantage point, inviting students to witness the interconnectedness of land and sea from a unique standpoint.

5.1 Voyage

Through its emphasis on coastal territories and the vast expanse of the sea, the Bauhaus of the Seas proposes a harmonious synthesis between nature (both human and more-than-human), technology, and the strategic goals of the NEB. It aims to explore how we can cultivate a sensitive, conscious, and balanced relationship with the planet's greatest common good, crucial for climate regulation, ecosystem preservation, and sustainable management of vital resources such as food, minerals, and energy.

In tackling complex socio-technical-ecological challenges, the Bauhaus of the Seas embraces the mission of applying design to address significant issues impacting the UN's sustainable development goals. It seeks to foster the design of intricate interactions between humans and the diverse array of non-human entities. This endeavor benefits from using digital technologies as a third space, bolstered by artificial intelligence, the internet of things, and digitally-enabled autonomy, enabling the manifestation of these interactions across vast temporal and spatial scales.

The design of these interactions not only gives rise to new aesthetics but also instills a critical awareness of their historical, contemporary, and future ramifications. By shifting the focus beyond human-centric perspectives, the Bauhaus of the Seas endeavors to secure a future for humanity. Guided by an ecocentric awareness, it proposes a reimagined

approach to the teaching and practice of design, transcending nostalgia, Eurocentric and anthropocentric viewpoints, and rejecting development based solely on relentless economic growth, resource extraction, and privatization of common goods and knowledge.

Emerging from the maturity of the digital revolution and encompassing the convergence of the physical, digital, and biological realms, the new Bauhaus embraces the opportunities presented by the fourth industrial revolution. The Bauhaus of the Seas responds by refocusing design as a discipline that actively conceptualizes and curates complex socio-technical-ecological systems revolving around the unique challenges and intricacies of the sea. It does so with a conscious commitment to distinct values, policies, and ethics, aiming to shape a sustainable and inclusive future.

The original Bauhaus was where ideas about the unity of art and technology began to take place and evolve. The Bauhaus of the Seas takes one step forward towards an aesthetics that celebrates from within (rather than merely analyzing from a distance) the inseparability of humans and nature. As a fresh vision for the NEB, the BoS is a practical example of how designers can mediate between top-down strategies and bottom-up initiatives, highlighting the importance of designing with and for radical interdependence. Embracing interdisciplinary collaboration, intergenerational learning, and interspecies understanding, the BoS embodies the core principles of the New European Bauhaus vision, offering a promising pathway towards a sustainable, inclusive, and beautiful future for all.

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